

WECOR

The Western Commission for the Study of Religion

The logo for the American Academy of Religion (AAR) features the letters 'AAR' in a stylized, gothic-style font.

AMERICAN ACADEMY OF RELIGION

Western Region

The logo for the Society of Biblical Literature (SBL) features the letters 'SBL' in a stylized, cursive font.

Society of Biblical Literature

PACIFIC COAST REGION

American Schools of Oriental Research

PACIFIC SOUTH WEST REGION

Annual Meeting Program Information

Fuller Theological Seminary
Pasadena, California
30-31 March 2008

...fostering excellence in the study of religion

O

The Western Commission for the Study of Religion

coordinates the annual meeting of these fine academic organizations,
dedicated to the study of religion, the bible, and archaeology:

the AMERICAN ACADEMY OF RELIGION, Western Region
the AMERICAN SCHOOLS OF ORIENTAL RESEARCH, Pacific NW Region
the SOCIETY OF BIBLICAL LITERATURE, Pacific Coast Region

On behalf of WECSOR, I would like to take this opportunity
to thank the following groups and people:

President Mouw and Fuller Theological Seminary
Mignon Jacobs
Fuller Theological Seminary's Student Volunteers
Joe DeRose
Ina Ferrell

AAR/WR Program Coordinator: Norris Palmer
SBL/PCR Program Coordinator: Tammi J. Schneider
ASOR/Pacific SW Program Coordinator: Beth Alpert Nakhai
Program Designer and Producer: Sonya Gravlee

If there is anything that you need,
or if there is anything that I can do to help make your conference experience better,
please do not hesitate to find me on the conference grounds, or to call me: 401-464-2180.

Enjoy the Conference, and Thank You.

William Krieger

**WECSOR is Proud to Welcome
its Exhibitors to our 2008 Conference:**

Please show your appreciation and support to our exhibitors,
who will be showing their wares in **Payton 101**
(next to Registration) for the duration of our conference.

Academic Christian Press

Amazzone Jewelry Sacred Adornment

Cambridge University Press

Edwin Mellen Press

Eisenbrauns

Hendrickson Publishers

InterVarsity Press

Life Bliss Foundation

Society of Biblical Literature Books

Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing Company

Zondervan

GENERAL INFO

WELCOME! It is a great pleasure to welcome the WESCOR 2008 convention to our Fuller Seminary campus in Pasadena. We gather as scholars in the various fields of religious research at a time when religion is much in the news, both in the political campaigns of North America and in a variety of cultural contexts around the world. Too often the role of religious belief in contemporary life is portrayed in negative terms, as strong religious convictions are viewed as a major contributor to the conflicts that plague the human condition. And sadly, these portrayals are often accurate. This is why it is so important for all of us who study religion to find ways to engage each other on matters that are not only of significant scholarly concern, but which also deal with some of the most basic concerns of the human spirit. Our deliberations together can not only provide a model for civil discourse about issues of ultimate concern, but our explorations together can also provide the kinds of insights that can demonstrate that serious engagement with religious questions can contribute to the well-being of the larger world in which we carry on our work. May it be so at this 2008 gathering!

Richard J. Mouw
President and Professor of Christian Philosophy
Fuller Theological Seminary

WESCOR is looking for groups and institutions to co-sponsor events for its yearly conference, both as a way to keep costs low for our members and also to give you the opportunity to highlight your organization at our meeting.

If you are interested in sponsoring a breakfast or reception that is on our regular schedule, or if you would be interested in adding one to the program, please contact the WESCOR office.

Local Maps and Information for WECSOR 2008 Pasadena, CA

Fuller Theological Seminary is located at
135 N. Oakland Ave. Pasadena, CA
Campus Maps will be provided to all participants.

The Hilton and Vagabond Hotels are located within a mile of the Conference.

FREEWAY MAP

ENLARGED STREET MAP

The Pasadena Hilton Hotel
168 S. Los Robles Ave.

The Vagabond Inn Executive
1203 E. Colorado Blvd.

AAR/WR SCHEDULE AT A GLANCE

SATURDAY 29 March 2008

Noon—5:30 PM	LOCATION
A1 Women's Caucus Lunch & Workshops	Geneva
2—6 PM	
A2 AAR/WR Board of Directors Mtg	Payton 102
2—6 PM	
A3 Queer Caucus Workshop	Walnut
5:30—7 PM	
A4 Racial/Ethnic Minorities Reception	Geneva

SUNDAY 30 March 2008

8:00—9:30 AM	SESSION I
A5 Religion & the Arts I	Psy 130
A6 Islamic Studies I	Psy 311
A7 Philosophy of Religion I	Psy 116
A8 Ecology and Religion I	Psy 120
9:45—11:15 AM	SESSION II
A9 AAR/WR Welcome/Plenary Address	Travis Aud
11:30 AM—12:45 PM	SESSION III
A10 Indigenous Religions	Psy 130
A11 History of Christianity I	Psy 120
A12 Religion in America I	Psy 314
A13 Women & Religion	Psy 311
12:45—2:15 PM	LUNCH
A14 AAR Section Chairs Meeting	Faculty Commons
A15 Queer Studies & Religion Lunch	Walnut
A16 Women's Caucus Lunch	Geneva
2:15—3:45 PM	SESSION IV
A17 Person, Culture & Religion I	Psy 314
A18 Jewish Studies I	Psy 116
A19 Ethics I	Psy 130
A20 Special Session: Goddess Studies	Psy 120
4:00—5:30 PM	SESSION V
A21 Women & Religion II	Psy 311
A22 Education/Workshops I	Psy 116
A23 Islamic Studies II	Psy 130
A24 Queer Studies/Jewish Studies	Psy 120
5:45—7:15 PM	RECEPTION
A25 WECSOR Reception	Carth Plaza
7:30—9:00 PM	SESSION VI
A26 AAR/WR Presidential Address	Travis Auditorium

MONDAY 31 March 2008

7:00—8:00 AM	BREAKFAST
A27 WECSOR Board Meeting	Payton 102
8:00—9:45 AM	SESSION VII
A28 Religion & Literature I	Payton 102
A29 Education/Workshops II	Payton 303
A30 History of Christianity II	Payton 302
A31 Person, Culture & Religion/Phil & Religion	DMin
10:00—11:45 AM	SESSION VIII
A32 Religions of Asia I	Walnut
A33 US Latina/o and Latin America I	DMin
A34 Nineteenth Century I	Payton 303
A35 Ethics II	Geneva
NOON—1:00 PM	LUNCH BREAK
A36 AAR/WR Business Meeting Lunch	DMin
1:00—2:45 PM	SESSION IX
A37 Buddhist Studies I	Ray Anderson
A38 Islamic Studies III	DMin
A39 Religion in America II	490 Conf Room
A40 Indigenous Religions/Women & Religion	Psy 120
3:00—5:00 PM	SESSION X
A41 Queer Studies in Religion I	Payton 303
A42 Pan African/Womanist I	Psy 116
A43 Person, Culture & Religion II	Psy 311

A# = AAR/Western Region Sessions

SBL/PCR SCHEDULE AT A GLANCE

SUNDAY 30 March 2008

12:45—2:15 PM	LUNCH
S1 SBL/PCR Board & Section Chairs Lunch	Payton 102
2:15—3:45 PM	SESSION I
S2 New Testament Texts & Traditions	Payton 301
S3 Hebrew Bible I: Torah/Pentateuch	Payton 303
4:00—5:30 PM	SESSION II
S4 Judaism in the Greco-Roman Era	Payton 302
S5 Hebrew Bible II: Prophets	Payton 301
S6 New Testament Epistles	Payton 303
S7 Open Session	Payton 304
5:45—7:15 PM	RECEPTION
S8 WECSOR Reception	Garth Plaza

MONDAY 31 March 2008

7:00—8:00 AM	BREAKFAST
S9 WECSOR Board Meeting	Payton 102
8:00—9:45 AM	SESSION III
S10 Qumran	Payton 120
S11 NT Epistles & Apocalypse	Travis Auditorium
S12 Hebrew Bible III: Writings	Psy 314
S13 Neo-Assyrian Insights...	Psy 311
10:00—11:45 AM	SESSION IV
S14 PLENARY ADDRESS	Travis Auditorium
NOON—1:00 PM	LUNCH BREAK
1:00—2:45 PM	SESSION V
S15 New Testament Texts & Traditions	Taylor 106
S16 Hebrew Bible IV: Psalms	Geneva
S17 Early Jewish/Christian Relations	Payton 302
3:00—5:00 PM	SESSION VI
S18 PRES ADDRESS/BUS MEETING	Travis Auditorium

ASOR/PSWR SCHEDULE AT A GLANCE

SUNDAY 30 March 2008

10:00—11:15 AM	SESSION I
01 Site Reports & Interpretive Frameworks	Geneva
11:30 AM—12:45 PM	SESSION II
02 Contextualizing the Data	Geneva
5:45—7:15 PM	RECEPTION
03 WECSOR Reception	Garth Plaza

MONDAY 31 March 2008

7:00—8:00 AM	BREAKFAST
04 WECSOR Board Meeting	Payton 102

SPECIAL MEETINGS: AAR, SBL, ASOR

MEETING

TIME LOCATION

Saturday, 29 March 2008

A1	Women's Caucus Lunch and Workshops	noon-5:30 PM	Geneva
A2	AAR/WR Board of Directors Meeting	2-6 PM	Faculty Commons
A3	Queer Caucus Workshop	4-6:30 PM	Walnut
A4	Reception for Racial/Ethnic Minorities in the Profession	5:30-7 PM	Geneva

Film: *Laundry and Tosca* <http://laundryandtosca.com/>
sponsored by the Brehm Center for Worship, Theology, and the Arts
by Burning Heart Productions: www.burningheartproductions.com

7:30 PM Travis Auditorium

A movie about being obedient to God's call on your life. Marcia Whitehead travels to New York for an audition with a world-renowned vocal instructor and begins her abundant life.

Contact person: Lynn Reynolds: lreynolds@fuller.edu

Facilitator: Lauralee Farrer

Sunday, 30 March 2008

A9	AAR/WR Welcome & Plenary Address	9:45-11:15 AM	Travis Auditorium
S1	SBL/PCR Board & Section Chairs Lunch	12:45-2:15 PM	Payton 102
A14	AAR Section Chairs Lunch Meeting	12:45-2:15 PM	Faculty Commons
A15	Queer Studies & Religion Lunch	12:45-2:15 PM	Walnut
A16	Women's Caucus Lunch	12:45-2:15 PM	Geneva
A25, S8, O3	WECSOR Reception	5:45-7:15 PM	Garth Plaza
A26	AAR/WR Presidential Address	7:30-9 PM	Travis Auditorium

Monday, 31 March 2008

A27, S9, O4	WECSOR Board Meeting	7-8 AM	Payton 102
S14	SBL Plenary Session	10-11:45 AM	Travis Auditorium
A36	AAR/WR Business Meeting Lunch	Noon-1:15 PM	DMin
S18	SBL Presidential Address/Bus Mtg	3:30-5:15 PM	Travis Auditorium

Schedule of Events

AAR

AMERICAN ACADEMY OF RELIGION

Western Region

Conference Theme:

NOON — 5:30 PM

A1 WOMEN'S CAUCUS LUNCH & WORKSHOPS

Geneva

Noon-1:30 PM — Luncheon: Mentoring for Graduate Students & Junior Scholars

1:45-3:30 PM—Workshop I: Women in the Academy (bring your question & concerns)

PANELISTS: SOUAD ALI, Arizona State University
 KAREN JO TORJESEN, Claremont Graduate University
 MARIE CARTIER, Claremont Graduate University
 TISA WENGER, Arizona State University

3:45-5:30 PM —Workshop II: Goddess Scholars Balancing Academic Career & Personal Practice

PANELISTS: HELEN HYE-SOOK HWANG, Global Ministries University
 NANÉ JORDAN, University of British Columbia
 PATRICIA MONAGHAN, DePaul University
 MIRANDA SHAW, University of Richmond *and others*

2:00 — 6:00 PM

A2 AAR/WR BOARD OF DIRECTORS MEETING

Faculty Commons

4:00 — 6:30 PM

A3 QUEER CAUCUS WORKSHOP

Walnut

THEME — *The Legal Status of GLBT People in Academia*

SHANE SNOWDEN, University of California, San Francisco

In this presentation, Shane Snowden will discuss what constitutes fair and equal treatment in academia, how institutions can ensure a welcoming environment beyond the demands of legal equity, and also review how they have been achieved in different types of institutions. She will draw on her eight years as LGBT Resources Director for the University of California system, which have included successful advocacy for all of the indicators and concerns above.

5:30 — 7:00 PM

A4 RECEPTION FOR RACIAL/ETHNIC MINORITIES
IN THE PROFESSION

Geneva

All those who consider themselves a racial and/or ethnic minority within the academy, their partners, and advocates are invited to attend a reception of light refreshments. This is an opportunity to meet like colleagues in the field, network, and have a good time.

8:00 — 9:30 AM SESSION I

A5 RELIGION AND THE ARTS I

PSY 130

THEME — Soaring and Settling of the Peripheralized within the Academy**HELEN HYE-SOOK HWANG, Global Ministries University, *presiding****Home Birth in the Academy: A Question of Methodology*

NANÉ JORDAN, University of British Columbia

Virgin Birth as a Holy Practice in Ancient Greece

MARGUERITE RIGOGLIOSO, Dominican University of California

The Art of the Practice of Mantra: The Tibetan Buddhist Goddess Tara and Her Mantras

KAREN NELSON VILLANUEVA, California Institute of Integral Studies

Metaformic Theory and the Evil Eye

CHRISTI COOK, New College of California

LAURA TRUXLER, California Institute of Integral Studies, *responding***A6 ISLAMIC STUDIES I**

PSY 311

THEME — Islamic Thought: Past and Present**SCOTT LUCAS, University of Arizona, *presiding****The Boundaries between Philosophy, Empiricism and Revelation in the Work of al-Biruni (d. 1048)*

MAHAN H. MIRZA, California State University, Chico

Interpreting Karbala: The Relationship between Doctrinal Shi'ism and Shi'i Ashura Rituals

SYED RIZWAN ZAMIR, University of Virginia

The Diversity of Islamic Reforms in Twentieth Century Indonesia and Malaysia

MUHAMAD ALI, University of California, Riverside

The Shadhduhuliyah Sufi Order in America: Liminality, Innovation and Tradition

ELLIOT BAZZANO, University of California, Santa Barbara

8:00 — 9:30 AM

SESSION I

A7 PHILOSOPHY OF RELIGION I

PSY 116

EMILY BENNETT, Claremont Graduate University, *presiding**Even a Trickle Gives Birth to the Mainstream: A Case of Hegel's Phenomenology of the Spirit and its Influence on the Contemporary Renaissance of the Trinitarian Thoughts*

CHUNG-HYUN BAIK, Graduate Theological Union

Hume's Challenge to the Emergence of Deity

PAUL DEVITTO, Claremont Graduate University

Why Science Needs Religion

KENNETH A. LOCKE, University of the West

A8 ECOLOGY AND RELIGION I

PSY 120

THEME — The Environment and Economies of Salvation

Other-worldly Eschatology and Marginalized Ecology or This-Worldly Eschatology and Ecology as a Central Concern

ANDREA M. STEPHENSON, Claremont Graduate University

Gift-Exchange with God: Taxation and Environmentalism

VINCENT BIONDO, California State University, Fresno

Ecofeminism and Environmental Racism: Religion's Role in Multiply Marginal Movements

SARAH ELIZABETH ROBINSON, Claremont Graduate University

9:45 — 11:15 AM

SESSION 2

A9 WELCOME & PLENARY ADDRESS

Travis Auditorium

JON STONE, AAR/WR President, *presiding**When God Plays Politics: An Opinionated Approach to the Study of Religion and Politics***Plenary Speaker: IVAN STRENSKI**

Holstein Family & Community Professor of Religious Studies, University of California, Riverside

11:30 AM — 12:45 PM SESSION 3

A10 INDIGENOUS RELIGIONS I

PSY 130

Dancing on the Edge of the World: Native Californians Reclaiming Their Center in Land, Song & Dance
JEAN MOLESKY-POZ, Santa Clara University

The Spirit of Ubuntu at Work in South Africa's Shift from Singularity to Plurality
SAMUEL PAUL, University of Southern California

The Invention of Paganism and Fetishism in African Traditional Religions: Reflection on the Colonization and Decolonization of Knowledge in Central Africa
MUTOMBO NKULU-N'SENGA, California State University, Northridge

A11 HISTORY OF CHRISTIANITY I

PSY 120

DYRON DAUGHRITY, Pepperdine University, presiding

Who Defines Evangelical Christianity?
DON THORSEN, Azusa Pacific University

Jansenism: Marginal Movement or Gallican Mainstream?
ELISSA MCCORMACK, Dominican School of Philosophy and Theology

Ellen White: Marginalizer or Mainstreamizer of Seventh-Day Adventism?
JULIUS NAM, Loma Linda University

A12 RELIGION IN AMERICA I

PSY 314

THEME — Re-Centering Non-Traditional Forms of Spirituality in America

JENNIFER RYCENGA, San José State University, presiding and responding

My Center, Your Periphery: A Relational Model for Spirituality in Globalized and Pluralistic America (on Traditional Chinese Medicine)
EMILY WU, Graduate Theological Union

Peripheral Visions: Using the Internet and Pop Culture to Bring Alternative Religions into the Mainstream
AUSTIN J. BUSCHER, Claremont Graduate University

New Religious Movements: Challenges for the Mystic Discourse
JODI LETTERMAN, University of California, Riverside

11:15 AM — 12:45 PM SESSION 3

A13 WOMEN & RELIGION I

PSY 311

DOE DAUGHTREY, Arizona State University, *presiding*

Ecclesiology in Feminist Thought: From Periphery to Center
ERIN BRIGHAM, Graduate Theological Union

*What of the Wo/Man's Place?: An Analysis of Gender in the Historiography,
Study, and Culture of U.S. Evangelicalism*
BEVERLY LUCAS, Arizona State University

12:45 — 2:15 PM LUNCH BREAK

A14 AAR/WR SECTION CHAIRS LUNCH MEETING Faculty Commons

A15 QUEER STUDIES & RELIGION LUNCH Walnut

A16 WOMEN'S CAUCUS LUNCH Geneva

2:15 — 3:45 PM SESSION 4

A17 PERSON, CULTURE, AND RELIGION I PSY 314

THEME — Religion and the Religious Subject in the Scientific Age

FRANZ METCALF, The Forge Institute, *presiding*

The Technological Tower: Eschatology and the Singularity
COLLIN BRAUN, Claremont Graduate University

*In Our Investigations of Religious Experiences, Spiritual Disciplines, Rituals and Ethics,
What Could be the Role of the Neurosciences?*
ERIKA WILSON, California State University, Los Angeles

*De-Centering the Violent Subject: A Psychoanalytic-Phenomenological Account of How
Non-Violence Works*
JOHN CHARLES ROEDEL, Graduate Theological Union

2:15 — 3:45 PM

SESSION 4

A18 JEWISH STUDIES I

PSY 116

THEME — Putting Jewish Women's Voices at the Center**EMILY LEAH SILVERMAN**, Graduate Theological Union, *presiding and responding**Iranian Jewish Women: The Domestication of Religion and Pilgrimage as the Center of Religious Life*
SABA SOOMEKH, Loyola Marymount University*Women and the Holocaust: A Jewish Feminist Perspective*
MICHELE FINAZZO, Claremont Graduate University**A19 ETHICS I**

PSY 130

KELLY A. FITZSIMMONS, Arizona State University, *presiding***PANEL DISCUSSION — Human Rights and Religion on the Sixtieth Anniversary of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights***Beyond Declarations: Reconciling the Relation between Religion(s) and Human Rights*
RICHARD AMESBURY, Claremont School of Theology and Claremont Graduate University*Feminist Critique of Human Rights and Religion: A Case Study of the International Convention on Human Rights*
KATIE SCHUBERT, Claremont School of Theology**A20 SPECIAL SESSION: GODDESS STUDIES**

PSY 120

THEME — Invoking Reality Through the Studies of the Goddess**LAURA TRUXLER**, California Institute of Integral Studies, *presiding**The Isis Navigium: Egypto-Greco-Roman Ritual of Antiquity Reconstructed in Contemporary Context—People Are Returning to Ancient Ways*

KAREN TATE, Isis Ancient Cultures Society and the Temple of the Goddess

Cows of Abundance: Ecological Lessons from Goddess Traditions
PATRICIA MONAGHAN, DePaul University*Kumari Worship Nepal: The Fate of the Royal Festival After the Dethronement of the King*
MIRANDA SHAW, University of Richmond*A Man's Search for the Goddess*
TIM WARD, Independent Scholar**HELEN HYE-SOOK HWANG**, Global Ministries University, *responding*

A21 WOMEN & RELIGION II

PSY 311

THEME — Spirituality in Female Form: Religious Traditions & Women's Embodied Spirituality**DOE DAUGHTREY, Arizona State University, presiding***Priestesses of the Goddess: Prophecy, Poetry, Midwifery, & Healing Among Early Mormon Women*
LAURA TRUXLER, California Institute of Integral Studies*The Dangers of the Feminine Form: How the Female Body is Portrayed in Jewish Writings*
CARLY SCHORMAN, California Institute of Integral Studies*All Acts of Love and Pleasure: Ethics and Sexuality in Modern Wicca*
MEREDITH BELL, California Institute of Integral Studies**A22** EDUCATION/WORKSHOPS I

PSY 116

THEME — Critical Thinking in Teaching Religion**KAREN CROZIER, Independent Scholar, presiding***Control the Language: A Key to Critical Thinking in Introductory Courses*
T. L. BRINK, Crafton Hills College*I AM MYSELF ALONE!: The Role of Critical Self-Reflexivity in Pedagogy and the Study of Religion*
SCOTT W. HODGMAN, Graduate Theological Union**A23** ISLAMIC STUDIES II

PSY 130

THEME — Political Islam**SOUAD ALI, Arizona State University, presiding***Defining Martyrdom, Recognizing Martyrs: The Battle of the Centers and Peripheries in Post-Revolutionary Iran*
SHAHLA TALEBI, Arizona State University*The Rise of Islamism in Turkey after the 1980 Coup: The Shift from Periphery to the Center*
SEMIHA TOPAL, Arizona State University*The Islamists in the Sudan: From a Party to a Corporation to a Republic*
ABULLAHI GALLAB, Arizona State University*The Veil in the Eye of the Beholder: A Central or Peripheral Constituent of Identity Negotiation?*
BAHAR DAVARY, University of San Diego

4:00 — 5:30 PM

SESSION 5

A24 QUEER STUDIES/JEWISH STUDIES

PSY 120

THEME — Examining Jewish Social Location and Religious Boundaries

DIRK VON DER HORST, Claremont Graduate University, *presiding**Situating Jewish Identity in the U.S.: Shaare Tefila Congregation v. Cobb as a Commentary on Jewish Social Location*

ANNALISE GLAUZ-TODRANK, University of California, Santa Barbara

Fences and Defenses

VICKI CABOT, Arizona State University

5:45 — 7:15 PM

RECEPTION

A25 WECSOR RECEPTION

Garth Plaza

7:30 — 9:00 PM

SESSION 6

A26 AAR/WR PRESIDENTIAL ADDRESS

Travis Auditorium

Prophecy and Dissonance, as Related to Festinger's When Prophecy Fails (1956)

JON R. STONE, California State University, Long Beach, 2008 AAR/WR President

7:00 — 8:00 AM BREAKFAST

A27 WECSOR BOARD MEETING

Payton 102

8:00 — 9:45 PM SESSION 7

A28 RELIGION & LITERATURE I

Payton 102

FINBARR CURTIS, California State University, Fresno, *presiding*

The Politics and Poetics of the Periphery: Religion, Gender, and Nation in the Poetry of Suheir Hammad
DEVIN KUHN, California Polytechnic State University

Kamala Das and the Public Secret
DANIEL MICHON, Claremont McKenna College

Carrying the Fire: On Being-Toward-Death and The Road
BRETT LAND, University of California, Santa Barbara

A29 EDUCATION/WORKSHOPS II

Payton 303

THEME — Empirical Research on Teaching Religion

KAREN CROZIER, Independent Scholar, *presiding*

Effects of World Religions Courses on Undergraduates: A Pilot Study of Tolerance & Contextualization
BRET LEWIS, Arizona State University

Teaching Comparative Contemplative Traditions: What is the Place of Practice?
SARITA TAMAYO-MORAGA, Santa Clara University
PHILIP BOO RILEY, Santa Clara University

A Theology of Vocation for Teaching Amidst Radical Diversity
ANNE CARTER WALKER, Claremont School of Theology

8:00 — 9:45 AM

SESSION 7

A30 HISTORY OF CHRISTIANITY II

Payton 302

RICK TALBOTT, California State University, Northridge, *presiding**Didache Community as Aristotelian Polity*

WILLIAM HASKINS, Azusa Pacific University

Appendix, Eclipse and Renaissance: The Trinitarian Thoughts in the 19th and 20th Century

CHUNG-HYUN BAIK, Graduate Theological Union

Martyrs, Hellenes or Both?: Religious Actors in a Locus of Power

MATTHEW RECLA, University of California, Santa Barbara

Wealth, Poverty, and Salvation

HELEN RICE, Westmont College

A31 PERSON, CULTURE, & RELIGION/PHILOSOPHY & RELIGION DMin**THEME — Bringing Gadamer's Philosophical Hermeneutics Towards the Center of Psychotherapy****AL DUECK**, Fuller Theological Seminary, *presiding***PANELISTS:**

ADAM GHALI, Fuller Theological Seminary

SCOTT GROVER, Fuller Theological Seminary

STEVEN HUETT, Fuller Theological Seminary

LISA FINLAY, Fuller Theological Seminary

JOSEPH P. BARSUGLIA, Fuller Theological Seminary

A32 RELIGIONS OF ASIA I

Walnut

THEME — Encountering the Sacred on Earth: Pilgrimage in Asian Cultures

Scholars Passing Through: Travelers' Accounts of Early Sikh Tradition
TOBY B. JOHNSON, University of California, Riverside

Shinran's Pilgrimage to Rokkakudō
KENNETH LEE, California State University, Northridge

Pilgrim Sites in South India: The Dual Roles as Monastic and Economic Centers
NALINI RAO, Soka University

King Pratapamalla's Pilgrimage
DEEPAK SHIMKHADA, Claremont Graduate University

A33 U.S. LATINA/O AND LATIN AMERICA I

DMin

THEME — Liberation Thought and Work from the Latina/o & Latin American Periphery

DANIEL RAMÍREZ, Arizona State University, *presiding*

Picturing Paradise: Cuadros from the Peruvian Women of the Pamplona Alta as Visions of Hope
REBECCA DAVIS, Graduate Theological Union

Rethinking Theological Method from the Periphery: A Latina/o Pentecostal Perspective
SAMUEL ALFARO, Fuller Theological Seminary

Shouts from the Latin American Periphery: Counter-Hegemonic Responses to the Neoliberal Political Economy
CHRISTY NEWTON, Graduate Theological Union

A34 NINETEENTH CENTURY I

Payton 303

JENNIFER ELISA VENINGA, Graduate Theological Union, *presiding*

The Blood Came Streaming Down: Linda Brent's Slave Narrative Moves Atonement Theory from Center to Margin
C.L. NASH, Edinburgh University

"Element of Perfection": Mormonism and the Nineteenth-Century Indictments of Race and Gender
KONDEN SMITH, Arizona State University

Gender, Sexuality and Civil Religion in the United States
ANN WERTMAN, Arizona State University

10:00 — 11:45 AM SESSION 8

A35 ETHICS II

Geneva

KELLY A. FITZSIMMONS, *Arizona State University, presiding**Manipulating Minds: Buddhism and Neuroethics*KARMA LEKSHE TSOMO, *University of San Diego**The Viability of Liberation Theology as a Response to Human Rights Crisis*PATRICK EMMETT, *University of California, Riverside**Process Model as Ethical Basis for Caring and Authentic Relations*ARLETTE POLAND, *Independent Scholar*

NOON — 1:00 PM LUNCH BREAK

A36 AAR/WR BUSINESS MEETING LUNCH

DMin

1:00 — 2:45 PM SESSION 9

A37 BUDDHIST STUDIES I

Ray Anderson

KENNETH D. LEE, *California State University, Northridge, presiding and responding**There Is No "There" There: The Insubstantiality of the World
According to Madhyamika and Quantum Physics*J. BRUCE LONG, *University of the West**A Buddhist Veneer on American Pop Culture: Beyond the Canon of Buddhist Studies*BROOKE SCHEDNECK, *Arizona State University**The "Marginal" Significance of Opening Chants in Chinese Buddhist Studies*NANYU CHEN, *University of the West*

A38 ISLAMIC STUDIES III

DMin

THEME — Teaching and Studying Islam in North America and the Arab World

SOUAD ALI, Arizona State University, *presiding*

Little Mosque on the Prairie: Microcosm of North American Muslims
SOHA YASSINE, Claremont Graduate University

Little Mosque on the Prairie: An Accurate Depiction of Islam?
TRACY HAWKINS, Claremont Graduate University

Little Mosque on the Prairie as a Teacher: A Critique on the Religious Educational Value
DUSTIN EATON, Claremont School of Theology

Qur'anic Schools for Older Yemeni Women: The Centrality of Literacy
SOPHIA PANDYA, California State University, Long Beach

The Indonesian Muslim Community of Arizona: Negotiating Religious Understanding
SAMSUL MAARIF, Arizona State University

A39 RELIGION IN AMERICA II

490 Conference Room

THEME — The (sort of) Mainstreaming of the Christian Periphery

JON R. STONE, California State University, Long Beach, *presiding & responding*

A. W. Trozer (1897-1963): American Fundamentalist Mystic
GLEN G. SCORGIE, Bethel Seminary

Sealing the Wall: President Kennedy's Religious Discourse
BENJI ROLSKY, Claremont School of Theology

Counter-Culturally Relevant: Sexual Abstinence in the Spiritual Marketplace
SARA MOSLENER, Claremont Graduate University

A40 INDIGENOUS RELIGIONS/WOMEN & RELIGION

PSY 120

JEAN MOLESKY-POZ, Santa Clara University, *presiding*

From Periphery to Center: Queen Ka'ahumanu's Use of Religion for Political Power
REGINA PFEIFFER, Chaminade University of Honolulu

Whose Periphery, Whose Center?
SANDRA STACEY, Graduate Theological Union/California State University, Long Beach with
BARBARA SKYTEARS MOORE, Dedonkohey Apache Medicine Woman

Return to the Center: The Case of the Philippines' "Cuidad Mistica de Dios"
OFELIA VILLERO, Graduate Theological Union

3:00 — 5:00 PM

SESSION 10

A41 QUEER STUDIES IN RELIGION I

Payton 303

THEME — Queer Publishing

MARIE CARTIER, Claremont Graduate University, *presiding*

Lisa Isherwood, Professor of Feminist Liberation Theologies, University of Winchester, will discuss Queer publishing, including ideas brought by those attending this session.

A42 PAN AFRICAN/WOMANIST I

PSY 116

THEME — Performing Power in the African American Church:
Gender, Consumerism, Liberation and Transformation

ARISKA RAZAK, California Institute of Integral Studies, *presiding**Between Centers and Peripheries*

MALIK JODAVID SALES, Graduate Theological Union

Worship as Public Transcript: African American Women and Gender Performance

PAULA MCGEE, Claremont Graduate University

The Head and Not the Tail—At Least Sometimes: African American Clergywomen, "Progressive Patriarchs," and Leadership in the Church and Home

MICHELLE STEWART-THOMAS, Mt. San Antonio College

A43 PERSON, CULTURE, AND RELIGION II

PSY 311

THEME — Scholarly and Personal Identities Between Center and Periphery

HESTER E. OBERMAN, Independent Scholar, *presiding**Praxis and Pedagogy: From Margin to Center in Religious Studies*

STANFORD J. SEARL, JR., Union Institute and University

Becoming Center—Periphery

MARIROSE K. LESCHER, Claremont Graduate University

Unreliable Narrators

J. CADE HARRIS, Claremont Graduate University

Schedule of Events

12:45 — 2:15 PM

LUNCH

S1 SBL/PCR BOARD & SECTION CHAIRS LUNCH

Payton 102

2:15 — 3:45 PM

SESSION 1

S2 NEW TESTAMENT TEXTS AND TRADITIONS

Payton 301

REBECCA SKAGES, *Patten University, presiding*

Mark's Disinterest in the Baptist Himself at His Death

FLORENCE GILLMAN, *University of San Diego*

Theodicy in Luke-Acts: A Mixed Message?

KENNETH LITWAK, *Azusa Pacific University*

Ignatius, Paul and Self-Effacement

KEVIN SCULL, *University of California, Los Angeles*

The Sending of Lazarus and the Tours of Hell Tradition

MATTHEW R. HAUGE, *Claremont Graduate University*

S3 HEBREW BIBLE I: Torah/Pentateuch

Payton 303

R. CHRISTOPHER HEARD, *Pepperdine University, presiding*

The Tablets of Testimony and a Reversal of Outcome in the Golden Calf Episode

CRAIG ANDERSON, *Claremont Graduate University*

Blasphemy, Talion, and Chiasmus: The Marriage of Form and Content in Leviticus 24

TIMOTHY M. WILLIS, *Pepperdine University*

Bearing Her Sin in Numbers 5:11-31

SARAH SCHECTMAN

Two Ends Against the Middle: Miriam as S/Hero of Numbers 12

JAMES FINDLAY, *California State University, Northridge*

Animals in the Prophetic World: Literary Reflections on Numbers 22 and 1 Kings 13

KENNETH WAY, *Talbot School of Theology*

4:00 — 5:30 PM

SESSION 2

S4 JUDAISM IN THE GRECO-ROMAN ERA

Payton 302

RANDALL D. CHESNUTT, *Pepperdine University, presiding**The Menorah and the Sun God: The Interweaving of Jewish and Pagan Motifs in Synagogues of Late Antiquity*VICTORIA ARMOUR-HILEMAN, *Hebrew Union College***S5 HEBREW BIBLE II: Prophets**

Payton 301

R. CHRISTOPHER HEARD, *Pepperdine University, presiding**A Diachronic Survey of Divine Warrioress Imagery in the Late Bronze Age, Early Iron Age I and Second Temple Period: A Comparison of Anat and Deborah*AMY MEVERDEN, *Fuller Theological Seminary**Lift Up Her Voice: Deborah, Hannah and Women's Psalms*LEAH REDIGER SCHULTE, *Claremont Graduate University**Splinters of the Calf: The Redactional Trajectory of Hosea's Calf Critique*JOEL HAMME, *Fuller Theological Seminary**My Dinner with Hosea: Food, Metaphor, and the Organization of Reality*RHIANNON GRAYBILL, *University of California, Berkeley**Reflections on the Question of the Servant's Death in Isaiah 52:13-53:12*SUE FRY, *Fuller Theological Seminary***S6 NEW TESTAMENT EPISTLES**

Payton 303

RON HOCK, *University of Southern California, presiding**Is God Paul's Patron: The Economy of Patronage in Pauline Theology*DAVID J. DOWNS, *Fuller Theological Seminary**The Meaning of Pistis Iesou in Romans 3:22 and 26 in Light of the Stoic Concept of Episteme*IRA J. JOLIVET JR., *Pepperdine University**The Hidden Transcript of Romans 13:1-7*REMI AUBUCHON, *Loyola Marymount University**Paul Was Not a Social Conservative: The Continuing Fateful Mistranslation of klesis in 1 Corinthians*S. SCOTT BARTCHY, *University of California, Los Angeles*

4:00 — 5:30 PM

SESSION 2

S7 OPEN SESSION

Payton 304

TAMMI J. SCHNEIDER, Claremont Graduate University, *presiding*

The Eros Jesusology and Cryptic Structure of the Gospel of Thomas: Plato and NHC II, 2 Gos. Thom.
WOOL MOON, Claremont Graduate University

The Role of Suffering in the Anti-Docetic Polemic of Ignatius of Antioch
STEPHEN E. YOUNG, Azusa Pacific University

Biblical Power: Sub-Strategies of Mediating the Transcendent Power of Scripture in P. Berlin 954
JOSEPH SANZO

The Literary Case for the Authenticity of Morton Smith's "Secret Mark" Episode
JOHN DART, *The Christian Century*

5:45 — 7:15 PM

RECEPTION

S8 WECSOR RECEPTION

Garth Plaza

7:00 — 8:00 AM BREAKFAST

S9 WECSOR BOARD MEETING

Payton 102

8:00 — 9:45 AM SESSION 4

S10 QUMRAN

Payton 120

HANNAH HARRINGTON, Patten University, *presiding**Self-Identification of the Qumran Sect*

BRIAN SCHULTZ, Fresno Pacific University

The Chronological Discussion in 4Q543-547 (Visions of Amram) and other Second Temple Works

ROBERT R. DUKE, Azusa Pacific University

4Q Pseudo-Ezekiel and the Apocryphon of Ezekiel

BRUCE HANSEN, InterVarsity Christian Fellowship

The Thanksgiving Hymns and Their Connection to Prophetic Literature at Qumran

JENNIFER M. PANTOJA, University of California, Los Angeles

S11**NEW TESTAMENT EPISTLES & APOCALYPSE** Travis Auditorium**RONALD F. HOCK, University of Southern California, *presiding****No Cursing in the Church: Anathema in the Corinthian Congregation (1 Cor 12:3) & Paul's Letters*

KENNETH L. WATERS, Azusa Pacific University

Sympathy for the De-Veiled: Paul's Mixed Messages to the Corinthians (1 Cor 11:2-16)

CALEB WEBSTER, Claremont Graduate University

Christian "Faith" Versus Judaic "Deeds of Torah": The Real Issue in Galatians

ALEXANDER LABRECQUE, University of Sheffield

Singing New Songs: Traditions in Conversation

KENDRA HALOVIAK, La Sierra University

Is the Gift of Apostle for Today?

KENNETH P. SEARLE, Patten University

S12 HEBREW BIBLE III: Writings

PSY 314

R. CHRISTOPHER HEARD, Pepperdine University, *presiding*

Reading Job 7:11-21 as an Anti-Prayer

JUN KIM, Graduate Theological Union

The Textual Evolution of a Verse: The Eunuchs' Assassination of Plot in the Books of Esther
LUCAS SCHULTE, Claremont Graduate University

Pilgrimage as Contested Discourse in II Chronicles 30

DALE LOEPP, Graduate Theological Union

Jealousy in the Hebrew Bible

PATRICIA POWER, Arizona State University

Unmaking Job to Make God: Reading the Poetics of the Book of Job through a Structural Analysis of Physical Pain

YOSEFA RAZ, Graduate Theological Union

**S13 NEO-ASSYRIAN INSIGHTS ON ANCIENT ISRAEL
AND THE HEBREW BIBLE**

PSY 311

BRAD E. KELLE, Point Loma Nazarene University, *presiding*

Where Is Your Bias?: Assyria and Israel—the State of the Question from the Assyriological Perspective
TAMMI J. SCHNEIDER, Claremont Graduate University

Assyria and Syro-Palestinian Political History: A Hebrew Bible Perspective
JEFFREY KUAN, Pacific School of Religion

משתין בקיר: An Echo of Divination in Biblical Hebrew

DUANE E. SMITH, Independent Scholar

The Portrayal of Assyria in the Book of Kings

MARVIN A. SWEENEY, Claremont School of Theology

S14 PLENARY SESSION

Travis Auditorium

"Assyria and the Westerners": The Role of Shalmaneser III in Assyria's First Expansion

K. LAWSON YOUNGER

NOON — 1:00 PM

LUNCH BREAK

1:00 — 2:45 PM

SESSION 5

S15 NEW TESTAMENT TEXTS AND TRADITIONS

Taylor 106

REBECCA SKAGGS, *Patten University, presiding**Political Undertones in the Sermon on the Mount*

MARCO AMBRIZ, Fuller Theological Seminary

A New Understanding of Jesus' Flesh in the Gnostic Influence on the Eucharist of John 6

JAE HYUNG CHO, Claremont Graduate University

Staying Connected: A Socio-Rhetorical analysis of Transitions in First John

BETH SNODDERLY, University of South Africa

Judging Compassionate Acts: Matthew 25:31-46 in Light of Second Temple Literature

PATRICK McCULLOUGH, Fuller Theological Seminary

Alexander, Herakles and the Politics of Matthew's Divine Birth Myth

RICHARD MILLER, Claremont Graduate University

S16 HEBREW BIBLE III: Psalms

Geneva

R. CHRISTOPHER HEARD, *Pepperdine University, presiding**The Position of the Torah Psalms in the MT Psalter*

ALAN LENZI, University of the Pacific

Context, Historical Method, Poetic Analysis, Spirituality, Postmodernism: Psalm 29, Psalm 23 and the Presence and Absence of God

CHRIS CORWIN, Graduate Theological Union

Too Close Yet Close Enough: An Exegesis of Psalm 32:1-7

JINA KANG, Fuller Theological Seminary

The Reclamation of the Lament: An African American Response to Walter Brueggemann's Article, "The Costly Loss of Lament"

HEIDE EDWARDS, Fuller Theological Seminary

1:00 — 2:45 PM

SESSION 5

S17 EARLY JEWISH/CHRISTIAN RELATIONS

Payton 302

JUDY YATES SIKER, Graduate Theological Union, *presiding*

Matthew's Interpretation of the Temple: A Factor in Deciding the Identity of Early Christian Communities
YONG HAN CHUNG, Graduate Theological Union

Jesus of Nazareth, the Pharisees, and Mediterranean Manliness
S. SCOTT BARTCHY, University of California, Los Angeles

Song of Songs: A Comparison of Midrash Rabbah and Origen
ROBERTA SABBATH, University of Nevada, Las Vegas

Guilty Yet Innocent: Two Intertextual Escape Clauses for Jewish Deicide in Augustine's Enarrationes en Psalmos
MARK BILBY, Point Loma Nazarene University

3:00 — 5:00 PM

SESSION 6

S18 PRESIDENTIAL ADDRESS/BUSINESS MEETING Travis Auditorium

YHWH's Call for Israel's "Return": Command, Invitation, or Threat
MIGNON JACOBS, Fuller Theological Seminary

Schedule of Events

American Schools of Oriental Research

PACIFIC SOUTH WEST REGION

Archaeology of the Ancient Near East

SUNDAY, 30 MARCH 2008

10:00 — 11:15 AM SESSION 1

01 **ARCHAEOLOGY OF THE ANCIENT NEAR EAST
SITE REPORTS AND INTERPRETIVE FRAMEWORKS**

Geneva

BETH ALPERT NAKHAI, The University of Arizona, *presiding*

The 2007 Season of the Renewed Excavations at Tel Gezer, Israel
GARY P. ARBINO, Golden Gate Baptist Theological Seminary

The Function of the Gate at the Iron Age Site of Et-Tell
CHRISTOPHER CLAREKE, Claremont Graduate University

The Iron Age Temple at 'Ataruz and Its Implication for the Ahab-Elijah Narrative in the Hebrew Bible
CHANG-HO JI, La Sierra University

11:30 AM — 12:45 PM SESSION 2

02 **ARCHAEOLOGY OF THE ANCIENT NEAR EAST
CONTEXTUALIZING THE DATA: METHOD AND MEANING**

Geneva

BETH ALPERT NAKHAI, The University of Arizona, *presiding*

Welcome Home Stranger: The Resident Alien in LBA Ugarit
MELISSA RAMOS, Fuller Theological Seminary

Jewelry in the Construction of Age and Gender Categories
ABIGAIL S. LIMMER, The University of Arizona

What Mean These Stones?: A Reappraisal of Iron II "Massebot"
RYAN N. ROBERTS, University of California, Los Angeles

Annales Archaeology and the Bible: the House that Lawrence E. Stager Built
DON C. BENJAMIN, Arizona State University

5:45 — 7:15 PM RECEPTION

03 **WECSOR RECEPTION**

Garth Plaza

MONDAY, 31 MARCH 2008

7:00 — 8:00 AM BREAKFAST

04 **WECSOR BOARD MEETING**

Payton 102

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Aubuchon, Remi	S6

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Bennett, Emily	A7
Bilby, Mark	S17
Biondo, Vincent	A8
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Y

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Younger, K. Lawson	S14

Z

Zamir, Syed Rizwan	A6
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